

Conflicts and Tensions in Urban Public Spaces: The Impact of Event Management

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ABSTRACT

The relationship between events and urban public spaces is increasingly marked by tensions and conflicts. This paper examines the various aspects of tensions related to event management in urban public spaces, highlighting the challenges faced by organizers, local authorities, and city residents. It analyzes strategies and solutions implemented to manage these conflicts, drawing on case studies from different cities and events. Key issues include conflicts over space usage, competing interests, environmental concerns, socio-cultural tensions, and security challenges. Effective conflict management requires enhanced communication and stakeholder consultation, efficient planning and coordination, environmental sustainability, and improved safety measures. The paper concludes with recommendations for integrated and adaptive policies to ensure the success and sustainability of urban events, promoting a harmonious coexistence between event activities and the urban community. Keywords: Conflicts, Urban public spaces, Events, Management strategies, Sustainability, Stakeholders

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between events and urban public spaces is increasingly characterized by tensions and conflicts. Cities such as Barcelona, Edinburgh, and Amsterdam face disputes over the use of public spaces for festivals, often prioritizing external benefits over local interests [1]. In Berlin, conflicts arise between those seeking leisure and those requiring quiet, leading to the identification of dedicated outdoor event spaces [2]. The pursuit of mega-events in Valencia has elicited social and environmental criticism from citizens and urban movements, revealing a clash between new urban modernity and local concerns. [3] These conflicts highlight the delicate balance cities must maintain between protecting public spaces as living resources and exploiting them for economic and reputational gains. The future of urban events could involve scenarios of persistent conflicts, harmonious growth, or increased digitalization. [4]

In light of these tensions and issues, it is imperative to develop effective management strategies to ensure the success and sustainability of events in urban public spaces. This involves enhanced communication and stakeholder consultation, efficient planning and coordination, environmental sustainability, and improved safety measures. We aim to examine the various aspects of tensions related to event management in urban public spaces, highlighting the challenges faced by organizers, local authorities, and city residents. We will also analyze the strategies and solutions implemented to manage these tensions and present case studies and concrete examples

from different cities and events. Finally, we will discuss future perspectives and recommendations for more effective and sustainable management of urban events.

I-LITERATURE REVIEW

Urban public spaces are the sites of numerous events that contribute to the vibrancy and attractiveness of cities worldwide. However, this activity is not without generating frictions and challenges that must be addressed to ensure a peaceful coexistence between events and the various stakeholders involved [4]

The literature review examines the various aspects of tensions related to event management in urban public spaces, highlighting the challenges faced by organizers, local authorities, and city residents. It also analyzes the strategies and solutions implemented to manage these tensions and presents case studies and concrete examples from different cities and events. Finally, it discusses future perspectives and recommendations for more effective and sustainable management of urban events.

The driving force behind the use of public spaces for events is often a neoliberal agenda focused on place marketing and revenue generation. Cities and event organizers are increasingly viewing public spaces as assets that can be leveraged to attract tourists, stimulate economic growth, and enhance the city's image. While this approach can bring economic benefits and increase the vibrancy of urban areas, it is important to acknowledge the broader implications of this neoliberal agenda. The prioritization of commercial interests and revenue generation can lead to the commodification of public spaces, undermining their role as inclusive and democratic sites.

To address these challenges, it is crucial to engage in a more nuanced and critical examination of the use of public spaces for events. This involves recognizing the complex interplay between the positive and negative effects of these events and developing strategies to mitigate the adverse impacts. Policymakers, urban planners, and event organizers should work collaboratively to ensure that the use of public spaces for events is balanced and equitable, taking into account the needs and interests of all stakeholders. By doing so, cities can harness the potential of public spaces to foster vibrant and inclusive urban environments while safeguarding their role as shared and accessible resources. [5]

The contested nature of public space reflects broader social struggles and ideological disputes over who has the right to access and use these areas [6]. Everyday interactions and unintentional spatial practices play a crucial role in shaping

public spaces, often creating exclusionary territories that are difficult to overturn even through collective action [7].

Cities, by their very nature, are dynamic and complex spaces that bring together a diverse array of social groups, each with its own unique identities, histories, and aspirations. This convergence often leads to social and symbolic conflicts, as different groups vie for recognition, resources, and control over urban spaces. The struggle for control is not merely about physical territory but also about the symbolic value and cultural significance attached to these spaces. [8]

Groups often develop their identities in relation to these urban environments and events, using them as canvases to express their cultural narratives, political views, and social norms. However, this process can also lead to marginalization, as dominant groups may impose their own values and identities onto spaces, excluding or displacing others. This can result in tensions, inequality, and even violence, as those who feel marginalized or disenfranchised may resist or challenge the prevailing social order. Therefore, the struggle for control of urban spaces is a complex and multifaceted process that shapes not only the physical landscape of cities but also the social and cultural dynamics that define urban life. [8]

Adapting public spaces to host events can initially seem like a practical solution, offering vibrant and accessible venues for community engagement and cultural expression. However, this approach introduces a new set of challenges and does not necessarily resolve existing problems associated with staging events in public spaces. Conflicts and disputes over the use of these spaces for events are almost inevitable, as different stakeholders—including residents, businesses, and event organizers—may have competing interests and priorities. For instance, while event organizers aim to create engaging and well-attended experiences, local residents may be concerned about noise, traffic, and disruptions to their daily routines. [9]

[1] Festivals and events in Barcelona and Edinburgh have given rise to tensions and disputes concerning the utilization of public spaces within their city centers, particularly in relation to issues of over-tourism and the privatization of public spaces. These tensions emerge when the staging of festivals and events in public spaces conflicts with other uses and users of those spaces, resulting in disputes among various stakeholders over access rights and usage priorities.

In Barcelona, the tensions are often exacerbated by the historical significance of popular festivities that traditionally occur in public spaces. The city's rich cultural heritage and deeply rooted traditions can lead to conflicts when contemporary events and commercial interests encroach upon these historically significant spaces. This dynamic creates a complex interplay between preserving cultural authenticity and accommodating modern event demands.

In contrast, Edinburgh faces more pronounced concerns over the overuse and commercialization of its limited public spaces. The city's compact urban layout and high concentration of cultural and historical attractions make it a prime destination for tourists, leading to issues of over-tourism. The intense demand for public spaces for events, coupled with the commercial pressures to maximize revenue, has resulted in disputes over the balance between public access and commercial exploitation.

Thus, while both cities experience tensions and disputes related to the use of public spaces for festivals and events, the specific nature of these conflicts differs significantly. Barcelona grapples with the challenge of maintaining the historical and cultural integrity of its public spaces, while Edinburgh contends with the pressures of over-tourism and the commercialization of its limited public areas. Understanding these nuanced differences is crucial for developing tailored strategies to manage and mitigate the tensions arising from the use of public spaces for festivals and events in each city. [1]

In conclusion, the use of urban public spaces for events, while contributing to the vibrancy and attractiveness of cities, also generates significant frictions and challenges that require careful management. The tensions arising from event management in these spaces reflect broader social struggles and ideological disputes over access and usage rights. To address these challenges, collaborative efforts among policymakers, urban planners, and event organizers are crucial to ensure that the use of public spaces for events is balanced and equitable, taking into account the needs and interests of all stakeholders.

II-METHODOLOGY:

This bibliographic selection on conflicts related to event management was conducted using a connection graph from Litmaps, a bibliometric tool that visualizes the relationships and citations between articles. The methodology focuses on identifying the most interconnected and cited articles to ensure the relevance of the references in this field.

data collection and analysis procedures:

- 1) **Definition of Keywords:** The keywords used in the search were "conflict" and "megaevent." These terms focus on the tensions generated by large-scale events, such as festivals and major sporting events, particularly in urban contexts. Conflicts may concern the occupation of public spaces, social tensions, or political resistance.
- 2) **Exploration of the Litmaps Graph :** Using the Litmaps graph, it was possible to visualize articles with the most interconnections through citations or common references. This graphical representation helped identify central articles, i.e., those frequently cited in the field of study. The densest connections were explored first, as they often represent the most robust and widely recognized academic debates.
- 3) **The articles were selected based on their relevance:** with consideration given to the following criteria: firstly, the number of citations, as articles that have been cited frequently are often regarded as being of significant importance within the field. Secondly, articles were selected based on their thematic relevance, with each article required to directly address the relationships between large-scale events (or mega-events) and the spatial or social conflicts they generate. Thirdly, a variety of methodologies were included to cover a range of perspectives on

urban conflicts around events, with articles employing diverse research techniques such as interviews, content analysis, and spatial analysis.

- 4) **Final Selection:** Among the analyzed articles, those with strong connections within the graph and directly related to the chosen keywords were retained. (See Table 01) This process provided an overview of the most relevant and influential publications in the field of urban conflicts related to mega-events.

Figure 1. "Literature Graph." This visualization represents the relationships between different research papers, showing how they are connected through citations and co-citations. source: The Author

Figure 2. "The Ring graph" in litmaps displays in the center of the circle the most important connection or primary paper of focus

The ring graph visually emphasizes the most significant connections by placing them at the center, facilitating a clearer understanding of their relevance in the context of other research works. This layout allows users to quickly identify key studies that have influenced a specific topic area, highlighting relationships and trends within the literature. By exploring these connections, we can better navigate the academic landscape, ensuring that they consider foundational works and emerging trends in their field of study.

To create the table (Tab.01) from the ring graph (Fig.02), we analyzed the central connections represented in the graph, identifying key papers and their respective themes. We categorized these papers based on their focus areas, such as urban

conflicts related to mega-events and public spaces. Each entry in the table includes the title, authors, year, summary, and methodology, providing a structured overview of the selected research. This approach helps clarify the interrelations among various studies while highlighting significant contributions to the field.

Title	Authors	Year	Summary
Tensions in Public Space (Barcelona, Edinburgh)	D. McGilivray	2022	Conflicts over public space due to tourism and privatization during events.
Events and Urban Space Policy (Netherlands)	Greg Richards	2024	Analyzes policy shifts impacting the relationship between urban events and public spaces.
Noise Conflicts in Berlin Open Air Events	C. Weber	2019	Conflict management between public leisure activities and urban quiet zones.
Mega Events and Urban Conflicts (Valencia)	L. Renau	2011	Mega-events reshape city image, sparking urban social movements.
Urban Spectacle Resistance (Louisiana Expo)	K. Gotham	2011	World Expositions highlight social inequalities and urban contradictions.
Homelessness and the FIFA World Cup (Rio)	E. Kassens-Noor, J. Ladd	2019	Mega-events create spatial conflicts, with homeless populations hidden from public spaces.

Table I. KEY PAPERS AND THEIR RESPECTIVE THEMES FROM RING GRAPH

III-DISCUSSION

1.Examination of Key Types of Conflicts Related to Event Management in Urban Public Spaces

Through our literature review, we examine the main types of conflicts associated with event management in urban public spaces.

1.1 Conflicts Over Space Usage: One of the primary challenges is the management of already limited public space and

the coexistence of various activities that take place there. Event organizers must negotiate space usage with other actors such as merchants, residents, local associations, and even homeless individuals . [10]These conflicts can arise due to competition for space, logistical issues, and the prolonged occupation of certain areas.

1.2 Conflicts of Interest: Events can also provoke conflicts of interest between organizers, local authorities, and residents. Organizers seek to maximize the impact and economic benefits of events, while residents may be concerned about disruptions caused by noise, traffic, safety, and property issues. Local authorities must find a balance between the economic and tourist interests of the city and the well-being of residents [2]

1.3 Environmental Conflicts:The organization of events can have a significant environmental impact, particularly in terms of the consumption of natural resources, waste production, and greenhouse gas emissions. Environmental concerns can manifest as conflicts with environmental activists, environmental protection organizations, or environmentally sensitive residents. Environmental sustainability of events is a key issue to minimize their impact on the urban environment [3]

1.4 Sociocultural Conflicts:Events organized in urban public spaces can also generate sociocultural conflicts. Certain groups or communities may feel excluded or marginalized by events that do not represent their identity or interests. It is essential to promote cultural diversity and inclusive participation to avoid such conflicts and encourage a fair representation of different communities . [10]

1.5 Security Conflicts:The safety of participants and the public is a major concern in the organization of events in urban public spaces. Potential risks such as terrorism, large crowds, management of people flow, and accidents may require enhanced security measures. Organizers and local authorities must take these aspects into account to ensure safety and peace of mind for participants and residents. [11]

These types of conflicts illustrate the intricate nature of event management in urban public spaces and the necessity for comprehensive and integrated strategies to address them effectively. These strategies emphasise the existence of divisions that manifest as competition over the use of public space and the right to reside in a particular area. [12]

2. Events and Daily Disruptions

Urban public spaces host numerous events that contribute to the animation and vitality of cities worldwide. However, these activities can create frictions and challenges that must be considered to ensure a peaceful coexistence between events and the various stakeholders involved. This section examines the main daily disruptions associated with events in urban public spaces.

2.1 Traffic Disruptions:Events can lead to temporary changes in traffic flow, including road closures, traffic diversions, and parking restrictions. This can hinder the movements of residents, workers, and visitors, resulting in delays, bottlenecks, and frustrations. Effective traffic management during events is essential to minimize friction and ensure smooth mobility.

2.2 Noise Disruptions:Events organized in urban public spaces are often accompanied by elevated noise levels, especially when they include musical performances, artistic displays, or fireworks. Such noise can disturb nearby residents, disrupt their tranquility, and cause inconveniences. Implementing measures to mitigate noise nuisances, such as reasonable event end times and the use of appropriate sound systems, is crucial for reducing these frictions.

2.3 Economic Disruptions:Events can have economic repercussions for businesses and enterprises located in the affected area. Traffic disruptions, reduced foot traffic from regular clientele, and access restrictions can lead to a decrease in sales and revenues for these establishments. Therefore, it is important to implement supportive measures, such as promoting local businesses during events, to mitigate these economic frictions.

2.4 Public Space Disruptions:The organization of events can also cause physical frictions within public spaces, such as the closure of parks, squares, or streets for the installation of stages, booths, or other temporary infrastructures. This can limit access to these public spaces, reducing opportunities for residents to engage in recreational activities and disrupting their customary usage. It is important to find a balance between the needs of events and maintaining access to public space for residents.

3. Costs and Responsibilities

Organizing events in urban public spaces requires financial resources and responsibilities from both event organizers and local authorities. This section examines the main aspects related to resources and responsibilities associated with event management.

3.1 Financial Resources for Organizers and Local Authorities

Organizing an event in urban public space necessitates significant financial resources. Organizers must account for expenses related to space rental, logistics (stages, equipment, public services), security, promotion, and communication. Local authorities may also bear additional costs, such as modifying public space, managing temporary infrastructures, and enhancing security and cleaning services. It is important to evaluate the resources committed to ensure adequate budget planning and guarantee the financial viability of the event.

3.2 Responsibilities in Logistics, Cleaning, and Security

Event organizers bear responsibilities related to logistics, cleaning, and security. They must ensure effective planning and management of logistics to guarantee the availability of necessary equipment, manage the flow of people, and coordinate various activities. Furthermore, they must implement measures to maintain the cleanliness of public spaces before, during, and after the event, establishing a proper cleaning plan. Regarding security, organizers are responsible for implementing appropriate safety measures to prevent accidents, manage crowds, and respond to emergency situations. They must collaborate with the relevant authorities to ensure that all regulations and safety standards are adhered to. Taking these responsibilities into account is essential for ensuring the successful execution of the event and the safety of participants and residents.

4. Conflict Management and Solutions: Communication and Consultation of Stakeholders

Conflict management through the organization of events in urban public spaces necessitates consultation with the stakeholders involved in the event. This section highlights the importance of involving residents, local merchants, local authorities, and regulatory bodies to find mutually beneficial and sustainable solutions.

4.1 Involvement of Local Residents and Merchants

Activities organized in the public space of a city can directly influence the daily lives of local residents and merchants. Therefore, it is essential to create a transparent dialogue with these interested parties to understand their concerns, needs, and expectations regarding the event. Public meetings and feedback sessions can be organized to foster an environment conducive to exchanging shared interests. By progressively involving these stakeholders in the decision-making process, it becomes easier to arrive at solutions that satisfy the interests of all concerned parties.

4.2 Dialogue with Local Authorities and Regulatory Bodies

Local authorities and regulatory bodies play a crucial role in managing events in urban public spaces. In this regard, establishing continuous communication with these entities is vital to ensure compliance with existing regulations and harmonize actions. Event organizers must remain constantly informed about administrative procedures, permitting requirements, and specific regulations related to organizing events in public spaces. By adopting a collaborative approach with local authorities and regulatory bodies, it is possible to address potential issues, anticipate obstacles, and ensure unwavering compliance with established norms.

The communication and consultation of stakeholders are of paramount importance in managing conflicts inherent in organizing events in urban public spaces. By proactively involving residents, local merchants, local authorities, and regulatory bodies, an environment conducive to seeking consensus solutions and resolving conflicts can be established. Transparency, active listening, and consideration of stakeholders' concerns undeniably contribute to building trust, reducing tensions, and promoting harmonious management of events in urban public spaces.

5. Effective Organization and Coordination

Successful management of events in urban public spaces requires rigorous organization and adequate coordination. This section emphasizes the importance of analyzing impacts and potential risks, as well as the necessity for precise spatial and temporal organization of events.

5.1 Analysis of Impacts and Potential Risks

Before organizing an event in urban public spaces, it is essential to carefully analyze the possible impacts on the environment, traffic, infrastructure, and the daily lives of residents. This includes identifying risks such as security issues,

traffic disruptions, and environmental noise disturbances. An in-depth analysis allows for the implementation of preventive and mitigation measures to reduce these impacts and ensure the safety and well-being of participants and residents.

5.2 Spatial and Temporal Organization of Events

A well-planned organization of public space is essential to guarantee safety, accessibility, and the conviviality of the event. This involves defining installation zones, circulation routes, access and exit points, as well as spaces dedicated to specific activities. Furthermore, temporal organization is crucial to avoid conflicts with other events, peak traffic hours, or sensitive periods in urban life. Close coordination with local authorities and stakeholders optimizes the use of public space and minimizes potential disruptions.

Effective organization and coordination are essential to ensure the success of events in urban public spaces. The analysis of impacts and potential risks allows for the prevention of issues and guarantees the safety of participants and residents. Similarly, rigorous spatial and temporal organization optimizes the use of public space and minimizes disruptions for the local community. By adopting a proactive approach and working closely with all stakeholders, it is possible to organize events that are both memorable and respectful of the urban environment.

IV. CASE STUDY BY TYPE OF CONFLICT:

The urban public space often hosts a variety of events that reflect diverse cultural, social, and recreational interests. However, these events can also give rise to conflicts among different stakeholders, including residents, local businesses, and regulatory authorities. The following table categorizes various types of conflicts that have emerged around urban events, illustrating the complexities of urban event management and the necessity for effective communication and stakeholder engagement to address these challenges.

The urban public space is the site of various events related to sports, culture, heritage, social issues, or urban planning. These events can generate conflicts of different natures among the concerned stakeholders. To resolve these conflicts, it is essential to implement effective management, maintain transparent communication, and engage in consultations among the involved parties to find solutions that satisfy everyone.

1. Analysis of Strategies Implemented and Their Effectiveness

1.1. Conflicts Related to Institutional Sports Events:

In South Africa, the choice of the stadium for the FIFA World Cup sparked several controversies (Alegi, 2008; Künzler, 2010). The initial bidding suggested constructing the stadium at Newlands; however, after the ANC gained power in the Western Cape province, Athlone Stadium was proposed. This choice was seen as a way to boost the development of football clubs in the poorer city areas, in contrast to the predominantly "white" Newlands Stadium. There was also the possibility of requesting a waiver for historical heritage, which was crucial for the bid's legitimacy.

Case Study	Example	Date
Conflicts Surrounding Institutional Sports Events	Opposition to the National Stadium Project for the 2010 FIFA World Cup	2006-2010
	Opposition to the Olympic Park Project for the 2012 London Games	2005-2012
Conflicts Surrounding Cultural Festivals	Opposition to the Sundance Independent Film Festival in the Historic District of Park City	1985
	Opposition to the Love Parade Electronic Music Festival in Berlin	1996-2010
Conflicts Surrounding Heritage Events	Opposition to the Demolition of the Tsukiji Fish Market for the 2021 Tokyo Olympic Games	2017
	Opposition to the Renaming of Streets Associated with French Colonialism in Algeria	2021
Conflicts Surrounding Facilities for Marginalized Groups	LGBTQ+ Pride Parade: Opposition and Controversy	2020
	Opposition to the Project for a Drug Addicts' Reception Center	2022
Conflicts Surrounding Major Urban Projects	Opposition to the Transformation of the Champs de Mars into a Tourist Destination	2021
	Opposition to the Creation of a Disney Park in Shanghai	2009
Conflicts Surrounding Places of Worship	Attacks on the Coptic Orthodox Church	2017
	Attacks on the Ghriba Synagogue	2002, 2023

Table II. CONFLICT CATEGORIES IN URBAN EVENTS

Due to the social housing surrounding the stadium, FIFA officials preferred Green Point Stadium, located on the city's outskirts in a wealthier, tourist-friendly area. The South African organizing committee immediately favored this option, which was later supported by the entire organizing committee of Cape Town and the Western Cape province. Even the mayor of Cape Town, an opposition member, eventually approved the construction of Green Point Stadium.

On one hand, the stadium would have the 60,000-seat capacity needed for a semi-final match; on the other, hosting the semi-final would attract more investments from both the provincial and central governments. Additionally, the stadium is situated by the sea at the foot of Table Mountain, creating an attractive setting for a globally significant match. Through this major international competition, Cape Town aimed to assert itself as a global metropolis.

1.2. Conflicts Related to Cultural Festivals:

Independent Sundance Film Festival in Park City: Dialogues were initiated between festival organizers (then called the Utah/US Film Festival in 1985) as issues arose between residents and local authorities regarding noise, traffic, and managing the influx of visitors. Adjustments were made, and these strategies helped reduce tensions.

Love Parade Electronic Music Festival in Berlin: A disaster occurred at the Love Parade electronic music festival in Duisburg, North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany, on July 24, 2010. Participants fell from the ramp into the festival area and suffocated, resulting in the deaths of 21 people attempting to escape, with 652 others injured. The Love Parade, an open music festival that began in Berlin in 1989, included stages and floats with music, DJs, and dancers interacting with the public. The Duisburg event marked the first time a festival was held in a prohibited location. Reports indicated the event drew crowds ranging from 200,000 to 1.4 million people, with 3,200 police officers present. Following the tragic events, the organizers announced that no further Love Parades would be held, leading to the festival's permanent cancellation. Legal actions were taken against the city of Duisburg and ten employees from the organizing company.

1.3. Conflicts Related to Heritage Events:

Demolition Project of Tsukiji Fish Market for the 2021 Tokyo Olympics: The local government spent hundreds of millions of euros to clean the new site. Tokyo Governor Yuriko Koike ultimately decided in late 2017 on the Toyosu site, considering the consequences of further delays on other construction work, particularly regarding access routes to Olympic facilities in 2020.

Project to Rename Streets Linked to French Colonization in Algeria: In the 3rd arrondissement of Marseille, the streets Bugeaud and Cavaignac have yet to be renamed, despite ongoing mobilization. Only Bugeaud School has changed its name. A notable success was in May 2021 when the Bugeaud Street school, also named after the marshal, was renamed by the new municipal majority resulting from a leftist alliance. The establishment now honors Ahmed Litim, an Algerian rifleman who died during the liberation of Marseille in August 1944. However, for the streets, nothing has changed; with each municipal election, the same demands resurface.

1.4. Conflicts Related to Facilities for Marginalized Groups:

LGBTQ+ Pride Parade in Warsaw: Despite opposition from some conservative groups, particularly the leader of the ruling nationalist party Law and Justice (PiS), Jaroslaw Kaczynski, who views the parade as a threat to traditional family values, security measures were implemented to protect the 20,000 participants and prevent violent incidents. Discussions also took place with local authorities to ensure respect for minority rights.

Drug User Center Project in Nice: Consultations were held with local residents to understand their concerns and needs. The mayor emphasized the "legitimate concern of neighborhood residents. According to him, such a center is incompatible with the safety of local residents, especially as this new facility is planned near a children's garden and educational establishments. Christian Estrosi also noted that passersby had recently been assaulted by drug users. Awareness and education initiatives were established to promote better understanding of issues related to drug addiction. Despite these efforts, some residents maintained their opposition. A petition was launched to prevent the opening of this drug user center, and a protest took place on November 3, 2022, at 3 PM in front of the Nice Foundation on Boulevard Tzaréwitch.

1.5. Conflicts Related to Major Urban Projects:

Champ-de-Mars Transformation Project into a Tourist Destination in Paris: An informational meeting was held on November 4, 2021, in the 16th arrondissement to present the project for greening and pedestrianizing areas around the Eiffel Tower. Local residents and elected officials expressed their opposition to this initiative. The renovation of Champ-de-Mars and Trocadéro continues to be debated. The project includes providing an additional 3.5 hectares for pedestrians and cyclists and creating 2 hectares of green spaces. However, this initiative did not receive unanimous support among local residents during the consultation, with some stating they had to drive due to their age.

On February 8, 2022, the Paris Council approved the redevelopment project, which encompasses the Iéna bridge, Trocadéro square, and Branly quay while excluding the northern part of Champ-de-Mars. Opponents and local resident associations were vindicated.

Case Study	Strategies Implemented	Effectiveness
Conflicts Related to Institutional Sports Events	Public consultations, compromises, open dialogue	Variable depending on cases
Conflicts Related to Cultural Festivals	Dialogues with residents, adjustments, security measures	Mixed results
Conflicts Related to Heritage Events	Discussions, negotiations, impact mitigation measures	Variable outcomes
Conflicts Related to Facilities for Marginalized Groups	Consultations, awareness-raising measures, education	Mixed results
Conflicts Related to Major Urban Projects	Public consultations, protection of residents' interests	Variable depending on cases
Conflicts Related to Places of Worship	Discussions, interfaith dialogue, enhanced security measures	Variable depending on cases

Table III. STRATEGIES FOR URBAN CONFLICT RESOLUTION

It is crucial to highlight that the efficacy of conflict resolution strategies can fluctuate contingent on a multitude of variables. [13] These variables may encompass the degree of opposition encountered, the capacity of stakeholders to reach an accord, the transparency of the decision-making process, and the consideration of the concerns of affected communities. Each scenario is distinctive, and the resulting outcomes may vary depending on the circumstances.

The following table outlines the various approaches that may be employed in order to manage and mitigate conflicts that may arise during large-scale urban events. The strategies are grouped into the following categories: communication, dispute resolution, community engagement, education, urban planning, policy and legislation, and cultural competency. [14]

Each category comprises specific tactics, the objective of these strategies is to guarantee that urban events are inclusive, harmonious, and beneficial for all parties involved, including event organisers, participants, and local residents.

Category	Strategy	Description
Communication	Open Dialogue	Facilitate discussions among organizers, participants, and locals.
	Active Listening	Ensure all parties feel heard.
	Public Forums	Host forums for community concerns.
Dispute Resolution	Mediation	Provide mediation services for disputes.
	Negotiation	Train leaders in negotiation skills.
	Restorative Justice	Address harm from conflicts through restorative methods.
Community Engagement	Community Policing	Build trust between police and residents.
	Inclusive Planning	Involve locals in event planning.
	Community Events	Host community activities alongside main events.
Education	Training Workshops	Provide conflict resolution workshops.
	Awareness Campaigns	Educate the community about event benefits.
Urban Planning	Temporary Infrastructure	Create temporary structures to manage crowds.
	Traffic Management	Develop plans to reduce transportation conflicts.
Policy and Legislation	Event Permits	Include conflict resolution provisions in permits.
	Data-Driven Approaches	Use data to identify conflict areas.
Cultural Competency	Cultural Exchange	Promote appreciation of diverse cultures.
	Multicultural Events	Organize events that encourage inclusivity.

Table IV. CONFLICT RESOLUTION STRATEGIES FOR URBAN EVENTS

CONCLUSION

While events can stimulate economic growth and promote city branding, they often result in the marginalisation of local residents and businesses. Cities such as Barcelona and Edinburgh are confronted with challenges associated with over-tourism and the privatisation of public spaces, which have the potential to give rise to socio-cultural friction. Another core issue is that of environmental sustainability. Large-scale events have been shown to generate significant waste and pollution, which can create conflicts with environmental groups.

It is of the utmost importance to engage with stakeholders in order to mitigate these conflicts. By fostering open communication and collaboration, as evidenced by case studies from cities such as Berlin and Cape Town, effective conflict management can be achieved. The efficacy of strategies such as transparent dialogue, negotiation, and mediation is contingent upon the willingness of stakeholders to cooperate and the specific context of the conflict.

The paper goes beyond the mere logistics and planning of events to address deeper societal issues, such as the struggle for power and control over public spaces. Urban spaces frequently serve as arenas for social and ideological disputes, wherein marginalised groups are either excluded or commodified for

the benefit of tourism and commercial interests.

In conclusion, it is essential to achieve a delicate balance between the economic benefits and the social sustainability of urban events. Event management must prioritise inclusive planning, stakeholder engagement and environmental responsibility in order to ensure that urban events are not only economically beneficial but also socially and environmentally sustainable.

The field of urban conflict management lies at the intersection of town-planning and conflictology. [15] By addressing the complex tensions and conflicts through collaborative and transparent approaches, cities can create harmonious and inclusive urban spaces that serve the interests of all stakeholders.

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